

Distribution of researcher-level funding allocation among U.S. federal funding agencies

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Abstract

This research-in-progress paper outlines the data collection approach and preliminary results of a study looking at the distribution of research funding from U.S. federal agencies. The goal of this project is to see whether the Matthew Effect, or cumulative advantage, can be found in the distribution of federal funding at the researcher level. The hypothesis of this study is that fewer PIs are being awarded larger proportions of the overall funding pool. This project studies the distribution of the number of grants and amount of funding per primary investigator awarded by eight federal funding agencies from 2008 to 2020. The preliminary results show that the concentration of funding varies across agencies.

Introduction

In this research in progress paper, we report the preliminary results of our project that examines the distribution of researcher-level funding allocation. We frame our research through the Matthew Effect. Matthew Effect, found in economics and a variety of other subjects, refers to a pattern in which those with an advantage tend to accumulate a larger advantage over time, whereas the disadvantaged grow increasingly so. It is a concept that has been evidenced at many levels in the scientific enterprise for example, the academic lineage of Nobel Prize laureates, and the citation-based reward system (Merton, 1968). In certain contexts, the Matthew Effect may be called by one of a few nearly synonymous phrases such as “Cumulative advantage” or “Preferential Attachment” as it’s known in network studies.

The allocation of funding is often discussed in the context of equity and excellence to understand if the allocation of resources via funding reflects the general distribution of research performance. Some argue that peer reviewers are not capable of allocating resources in a way that mirrors the actual distribution of productivity and performance, and that their judgement in excellence of research may be flawed (Hicks and Katz, 2011). As a result, experiments on dispersal research funding are carried out (Aagard et al., 2020) to answer which system, concentrated funding vs. dispersed funding, is better suited for supporting scientific progress. On one hand, advocates of funding concentration cite economies of scale and access to more institutional resources among others for continuing to dole out purely merit or excellence-based funding. On the other hand, advocates for increased dispersal of funds argue that the benefits of an updated system would include the creation of a diverse research ecology, more opportunities for students and institutions lacking resources, and increased productivity.

One area which has been discussed at length but has not sufficiently been empirically analyzed is the impact of the effect on the allocation of scientific funding by U.S. federal funding agencies. The overarching goal of the project is to test the hypothesis that the Matthew Effect can be seen in the allocation of research funds where fewer PIs are being awarded larger proportions of the overall funding pool. In this RiP, we report the data collection approaches and preliminary results.

Materials and methods

In this research in progress paper, we focus on the descriptions of a complex process to obtain the suitable data for this research. Initial raw data, containing award data for eight federal agencies from 2008 through 2020, was collected through the Federal eXporter. The data was collected in February 2021 just prior to the retirement of the platform in March, 2021. The agencies include the Department of Defense (DoD), the Department of Education (ED), the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Health and Human Services (HHS), the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the National Science Foundation (NSF), the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), and the Veterans Association (VA). A different portal is available with data on various federal agencies' budget and spending called USASpending.gov. After exploring the data available on this portal, we decided the data were not suitable to our needs as specific details about awards and grants such as the names of primary investigators and institutions.

Some of the federal agencies did not have data reported in Federal eXporter for various years. We discovered this by manually looking through each years' export from 2008 to 2020 and recording the number of awards for each federal agency in the chart below.

To have as complete of a dataset as possible, we collected supplemental award reporting data from each agency's individual portals¹:

Table 1. Number of funded projects across agencies

Year	DOD	ED	EPA	HHS	NASA	NSF	USDA	VA
2008	756	114	203	85468	2460	11696	3492	-
2009	964	143	143	96127	2004	15299	3704	315
2010	845	166	343	91137	1903	13632	3531	8
2011	672	149	271	79748	1622	11736	3178	836
2012	574	134	238	75333	1379	11813	3015	880
2013	690	205	113	73168	1569	11440	3348	1103
2014	909	283	199	71964	1647	11290	3143	1508
2015	934	386	208	71739	1757	12147	3346	1747
2016	854	406	84	71207	1385	12716	3111	1363
2017	909	441	68	71789	512	12231	1066	1406
2018	932	493	44	79337	9026	12603	1244	1602
2019	2339	168	41	77012	9461	12104	1218	1838
2020	1693	162	56	79295	9393	12979	-	2148

¹DoD: <https://dodgrantawards.dtic.mil/grants/#/advancedSearch>

ED: <https://ies.ed.gov/funding/grantsearch/index.asp>

EPA: <https://cfpub.epa.gov/ncer/abstracts/index.cfm/fuseaction/searchControlled.main?RequestTimeout=180#>

NASA: <https://www.nasa.gov/centers/nssc/forms/grant-status-form>

USDA: <https://cris.nifa.usda.gov/cgi-bin/starfinder/68998/crisassist.txt>

VA award data was not found

The data sources included Federal Exporter data, DoD supplemental data, ED supplemental data and EPA supplemental data. NASA supplemental data was excluded because it did not have information about project total cost.

First, we merged data from all the investigated years and at the same time, a total of 233,738 projects in the Federal Exporter data with missing information in the fields such as PI, institution or total cost were removed. After removing duplicates during the integration of data from multiple sources, a total of 1,031,747 projects remained. For the projects with missing start or end dates, we imputed data with the following heuristics. If a start date was missing, we set January 1st of the project fund year as the start data. If an end date was missing, we checked the project’s duration, and the end date was calculated by adding the duration to the start date. If project duration was also missing, December 31st of project fund year was set as the end date. After all the above-mentioned pre-processing steps, a total of 1,031,287 projects were included in the final dataset. Projects with multiple PIs were assigned separately to each of the PIs with all the information are the same except for the PI information.

Second, we removed projects that had not been awarded to researchers affiliated with higher education institutions. To identify higher education institutions, all the organization names were uppercased, and organizations that include UNIVERSITY, UNIV, COLLEGE, SCHOOL, INSTITUTE, and INSTITUTION in their names were selected. We manually reviewed the remaining organizations and found additional 21 higher education institutions that were included in the data. In total, we removed 182,801 projects that had not been awarded to researchers of higher education institutions.

Third, we used a pretrained deep learning model SBERT (Reimers, N., & Gurevych, I., 2019) to conduct PI name disambiguation. The dataset has a total of 260,463 unique names while 12.08% of them appeared twice or more with different organization names. As Table 2 shows, most names (99.95%) affiliated with fewer than six institutions. We removed the PIs whose name were affiliated with more than five institutions and conducted PI name disambiguation for the reaming 260,335 names.

Table 2. Unique names and the number of affiliated institutions

# of affiliated institutions	1	2	3	4	5	6+
# of Names	229,006	27,319	3,320	546	144	128

We investigated titles of the projects, which are the only text information that these different platforms have in common, to identify the same author affiliated with more than two organizations, mainly due to movement. SBERT was used to calculate project title similarity and if two PIs with the same name, but affiliated with different organization, have their similarity of project titles above a certain threshold, we treated them as the same PI. To derive the threshold, we divided all PIs into three types as follows:

- Group A. PIs with different name. (They are treated as different PIs.)
- Group B. PIs with same name and same institutions. (They are treated as same PIs.)
- Group C. PIs with same name but different institutions. (Need to be disambiguated.)

We used project titles from Group A to calculate the maximum value of the sentence similarity between two totally different PIs. 100,000 pairs of two different names from Group A were randomly chosen. We then calculated the sentence similarity using SBERT between each pair of names’ project titles. Each name had one or more project titles, so we calculated the sentence

similarity for all the combinations and kept the largest value. Because different PIs may work on the same project which will cause the sentence similarity to be one and affect the value, the pairs with same project titles were not included. Table 3 shows the results.

Table 3. Similarity scores of the group of different PIs

Percentile	Mean	50%	75%	98%	98.1%
Similarity score	0.07	0.06	0.13	0.34	0.35

Next, we used project titles from Group B to calculate the sentence similarity for the same PIs. Table 4 shows the result.

Table 4. Similarity scores of the group of different PIs

Percentile	Mean	25%	50%	75%
Similarity Score	0.53	0.35	0.53	0.72

From the two tables above, we can see that 98% of project titles' sentence similarity from different PIs were lower than 0.35, and 25% of project titles' similarity from same PI are lower than 0.35. So, we chose 0.35 as the threshold to conduct PI disambiguation. If two PIs in the Group C has at least one computed similarity score that is above 0.35, we treated them as the same PI.

Fourth, we used Namsor API (<https://namsor.app>), which relies on name and country information, to assign genders to PIs. Each PI name was assigned two probabilities, one for each gender. If the probability is less than 90%, then we treated it as U(ndecided)

The resulting work sheet contains PI's ID, name, gender, the number of projects (NIH, NSF, and others) the PI had at a given month and the dollar amount. Table 5 shows an example.

Table 5. Sample records in work sheet

ID	PI	Gender	Month	NIH#	NSF#	OTHERS#	NIH\$	NSF\$	OTHERS\$
9527	Smith, Adam	M	20-Jan	1	2	0	\$20,000	\$12,000	0
9527	Smith, Adam	M	20-Feb	1	2	0	\$20,000	\$12,000	0
9527	Smith, Adam	M	22-Mar	2	1	0	\$23,000	\$5,000	0

Preliminary results

The results show that NIH, NSF, and other agencies exhibit different distribution patterns: for NIH, the average number of active grants per PI at any given month declined from more than five projects per PI at any given month in the late 2000s to around two projects in the late 2010s. The number should be interpreted as in the late 2000s, for any researcher with active NIH funding, on average, each researcher was leading five projects at any given month in that period. The pattern is almost monochroic with few minor up ticks. For NSF, there is a noticeable upward trend from the late 2000s to early 2010s, likely due to the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act (ARRA) of 2009 that allocated additional funding to the agency. Once the funded faded out, the number of per PI grants went downward. Between 2013 and 2020, there is a seemingly concentration of grants on PIs as the number of active grants per PI at any given month went up from 0.4 to 0.5. For other agencies combined, the concentration of funding allocation was peaked in 2013 then declined since then.

The level of the concentration of funding allocation varies across agencies. It is due to the ways investigators are reported in those agencies. NIH does not consider co-Pis but multi-institutional Pis whereas co-PI information is collected and reported by NSF. Throughout the data collection period, we did not find any major changes in how investigators were counted in those agencies; thus, the collection method should not be considered as an artifact.

Figure 1. Average number of funded projects per PI at any given month between 2008 and 2022

Conclusion

The allocation of funds and resources has been studied by many; however, much of the current literature either investigates the Matthew Effect on grants of a small scale like institutional funding or at large aggregated scales like global funding (Bloch and Sørensen, 2015). Our project finds its niche examining the characteristics of the distribution of funds from U.S. federal agencies at the researcher level. At this stage, we have completed the data collection process and are continuing analysis to test our overall hypothesis that the Matthew Effect can be found in the allocation of research funds. As part of our future work, we intend to examine what impact the probable gender of the researcher has, if any, on this effect. This work may have broad impact because while taxpayer dollars fund these research endeavours, the taxpayer almost never knows or has any say in how funding is distributed. This has serious implications when operating within the understanding of science as a public good.

References

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